

INTEGRATION OF PRINCELY STATES AFTER INDEPENDENCE

Harpreet Kaur

Principal, Guru Nanak Khalsa College, Daroli Kalan, Jalandhar

ABSTRACT

At the time of Indian independence in 1947, there were approximately 565 princely states within British India. These states were not part of the British provinces but were ruled by Indian rulers under the suzerainty of the British crown. Following independence, these states were given the option to join either India or Pakistan, or remain independent. At the Dawn of Independence, being convinced that the princely states should form a part of the overall Union of India, Sardar Patel wanted that democratic governments should be established in the states and the princes should join the Union of India as the federating units. In the process of nation-building, he wanted the citizens of the states to join him. He believed that the will of the people is supreme, and sovereignty rested not with the king but with the people only.

Keywords: Accession, Democracy, Nationalism, Paramountcy, Princely States,

INTRODUCTION

Even in the earlier stages of the Indian civilization there had rarely been an occasion when the whole country had completely been under a single government. The political integration of the country was never possible. The beginning of the British domination in India was, basically, through a series of treaties with the various rulers of the country from time to time. Even after deploying the armed forces, the British Government was not fully successful in extending its control to the entire country, it had to enter into treaties with powerful native kings. Till the breaking out of the First World War, Nationalism in India did not grow to such an extent as to pose a threat to the British rule. There was no upsurge of mass consciousness for the establishment of a responsible Government in the country.

THE PARAMOUNTCY

Paramountcy was a special system concerning the relationship of the states with the British government. The states had to cooperate with the government on matters of all-India policies in respect of railways, post and telegraphs, and defense. The crown representatives sometimes used to station an army, construct railways on a part of the states, and used to take the administrative control of the area. States had a series of agreements with the British government. In addition to that, the crown representative could seek military assistance from the government of India in case he found it necessary for the protection of the ruler from external aggression or an internal revolt. The position of the Indian states and their relation with the British Government were well defined through various treaties and declarations by the British Government from time to time. The position of the states became very much critical at the time of the transfer of power in 1947. It was a question whether with the lapse of Paramountcy, the states would attain complete freedom or not. There were two possibilities with regard to the position of the states after the lapse of Paramountcy

The states might become completely free and independent sovereign states without having any control exerted over them by the two newly formed states of India and Pakistan. Such a proposition would have led to the complete Balkanization of the country.

With the withdrawal of the British power, the states would develop new relationship with either of the states-India or Pakistan, depending upon the geographical continuity and

political situation prevalent. In order to maintain the unity of the country, such a solution was a must, but it was difficult to ascertain whether the Princess of the states, liked to surrender their power and join the newly formed states as federating units. The Cabinet Mission Plan of 16th May, 1946 gave a clear picture of the transfer of power and the position of the native states in the new setup of free India. It stated that provision shall be made for the participation of the Indian states in the constitution making body. His Majesty's Government undertake to accept the right of any province of British India that is not prepared to accept the new constitution to retain its present constitutional position, provision being made for subsequent accession if it so decides. The options available to the States Therefore, the problem arose due to the British policy towards more than five hundred Princely States, their exact position after the departure of the British was not clearly defined. The native princes were allowed to join either of the two proposed countries according to their choice. A country, invested with such a large number of Free states, could not have dreamt of political consolidation in such an environment. It was quite likely that those princess could have formed a third force and contributed towards its disintegration rather than its further consolidation. Faced with such a critical and complex situation, the mantle of finding out a solution fell upon Sardar Patel. By tactful method, by promising privy purses, through his friendly advice, and sometimes by stern and strong administrative measures, he could succeed in bringing all the rulers together merging their states into the Indian union without any bloodshed.

As per the clauses of the Cabinet Mission Plan of May 16th the states were to send 93 representatives to the Constituent Assembly and the Princely states would be represented by a Negotiating committee. Patel realized that in order to counteract any design by the Princes, the Congress and the Constituent Assembly, should hold full powers. Accordingly, on December 21st, 1946, K.M. Munshi moved a resolution in the Constituent Assembly that there should be a committee to confer with the Negotiating Committee of the States regarding the distribution of 93 seats allocated to the States in the Constituent Assembly. To negotiate with the various states, a new department called "States Department" was formed and Patel assumed its office on 5th July 1947. As early as December 7, 1946, Patel made it clear that the Constituent Assembly would have the real authority to decide about the grouping of the states. Dr. Ambedkar too wanted that the native states should merge with the Indian Union and the States should realize that they could not remain independent, having only geographical boundaries with India and by acting against the will of the people. After assuming office of the States Department, Sardar Patel defined the policy of the Government of India with regard to the Princely states and persuaded them to accede to the Dominion of India on the subjects of Defense, Foreign Affairs and Communications.

APPROACH OF SARDAR PATEL

Patel did not like to have confrontation with the rulers unless otherwise compelled. His approach towards the princes was a peaceful one, with friendly advice and psychological treatment, but he did not rule out confrontation as the last resort. He explained that by acceding to the Indian Union the future of the country, and simultaneously the future of the princely states, would be brighter, even peace would return to the country. He thus gave a personal touch to the problem of the princely states by considering the princes as his friends and was sure that his appeal would rouse patriotism in the minds of native rulers. Patel's approach to the princes was multifarious in its composition. He knew that his appeal to the princes might not influence all the rulers. Some rulers, who would not respond to his appeal, would need a different but a stronger treatment. When his appeal failed, Patel did not hesitate to go to the extent of warning the princes with the worst consequences. He indicated that at the moment when the country was facing a heavy foreign onslaught, the princes must follow

the line of thinking of the government and the citizens of the respective states. He even pointed out that he would not hesitate even in taking strong measures with military contingence. In spite of his strong action and warning, Patel behaved most sympathetically and realistically with the rulers. He persuaded the rulers to accede to the Indian Union and convinced them that there was no other alternative to accession. He also created popular opinion among the citizens of the native states, regarding the idea of merging with India. The tremendous changes of bringing the states under the banner of the Indian Union were brought about in a short span of two years. The entire process went on peacefully through democratic and peaceful means without the use of any military power, except in case of Hyderabad. Initially the rulers' response was not favourable as most of them thought about their own sovereignty after the lapse of Paramountcy. The attitude of the rulers, however, softened when they took a realistic stock of the situation. Patel urged that the states, which were already represented in the Constituent Assembly, should immediately accede in respect of three subjects which would enable them to have a direct voice in shaping the policy of the Central Government.

The States' Negotiating Committee, headed by Sardar, finalized the draft of the Instrument of Accession and Standstill Agreement on July 31st, 1947. Patel kept the sacrifice of the rulers foremost in mind, he tried to look after their interests by safeguarding the payment of their privy purses. He also acknowledged the ability of some of the rulers by appointing them as Rajpramukh and afterwards as Governors or Ambassadors. It was Patel's large-heartedness that enabled him to ensure that the rulers did not find them in hardship after relinquishing their offices. The process of integration was so quick that by 15th August, 1947, all the native states except Hyderabad, Junagadh and Kashmir signed the Instrument of Accession.

THE INTEGRATION AND AFTERMATH

The accession of Indian States went side by side with their physical integration and reorganization, 310 states were organized into six unions while 215 were merged with their neighbouring provinces. Another 5 states were converted into Chief Commissioners' Provinces, but Hyderabad and Mysore were left untouched initially. In all 15 administrative units came into existence by the late 1940s. Responsible Governments were set up in all these units, and the former rulers were given the title of "Raj Pramukhs". Besides, they were allowed to retain their personal privileges, and tax-free privy purses were granted to them. The 1956 reorganisation of states has left almost all the former states totally changed. It may be observed that in his approach to the problems of princely states, he had some strategic considerations.

- The first step of acceding to the Union in respect of three subjects was a wise decision, as it was acceptable to the rulers due to their inexperience in those matters.
- Patel was fully aware of the political, social and economic conditions of the various states. He knew the weakness of the princes of such states, so he tried to take advantage of the situation.
- Patel could take Mountbatten into full confidence and the cabinet entrusted the viceroy to negotiate with the rulers regarding the accession and also to deal with Hyderabad.
- He wanted not only in geographical integration but also social and economic integration. He knew that once the country was integrated geographically, it would be easier to undertake the work for social, constitutional and financial harmony.
- Patel felt that the payment of privy purses was not a big thing in comparison to the amount spent by the rulers. He appealed to the members to give a realistic consideration to that aspect

and agreed with him. Sardar, however, kept the issue open to review at a later date by carefully formulating the provision of the Privy Purse. Unlike the scheme of 1935 our new constitution is not an alliance between democracies and dynasties, but really a union of the Indian people built on the basic concept of sovereignty of the people. It removed all barriers between the people of the states and the people of provinces and achieves for the first time the objective of a strong democratic India". Constitutionally, all the states came under the Indian Union on November 26th, 1949 when the members signed the final draft of the constitution. Six years thereafter came the States' Reorganisation Act and reference to Part-B states was removed and the princely states merged into the Indian Union in all respect. Patel's efforts for the constitutional guarantee of the privy purse met with a lot of opposition and in 1971, through the 26th Amendment to the constitution, Articles 291 and 362 were repealed with effect from December 28, 1971 and with the introduction of Art 363A, the provision of the privy purse granted to the Rulers of the erstwhile Indian States and certain personal privileges granted to them had been taken away

The limited scope of the Instruments of Accession and the promise of a wide-ranging autonomy and the other guarantees they offered, gave sufficient comfort to many rulers, who saw this as the best deal they could strike given the lack of support from the British, and popular internal pressures. Between May 1947 and the transfer of power on 15 August 1947, the vast majority of states signed Instruments of Accession. A few, however, held out. Some simply delayed signing the Instrument of Accession. The biggest problems, however, arose with a few border States

- Junagadh- actually did accede to Pakistan
- Hyderabad and Kashmir- declared that they intended to remain independent.

JUNAGADH- ACCESSION, CHAOS AND AFTERMATH

Junagadh created a big problem for the solidarity of the country. It was one of the strongest States in Saurashtra at that time and was ruled by a Muslim ruler but the inhabitants were mostly Hindus. The ninth and the last Nawab Mohammad Mahabat Khanji III ascended the throne as a minor on the January, 22, 1911. He was at the helm of affair till 1947, when the drama of the instrument of accession unfolded at Junagarh. In the last months of British India his dewan was a Muslim League politician named Shah Nawaz Bhutto (father of future Pakistani Prime Minister Zulfikar Bhutto). In the beginning, Junagadh assured that it would accede to India. Till 14th August, 1947, Junagadh did not accede either to India or to Pakistan. However, on 15th August, 1947, the people of the state were shocked on hearing that the state had acceded to Pakistan and that the accession had been accepted by the other party. The Government of India press Communiqué dated 25th September, 1947, strongly denounced such action of Nawab and asserted firmness in dealing with the situation. Under the leadership of Shamaldas Gandhi, Kathiawad People's Front was formed to mobilize people to step up the efforts from within to join India. It was decided in New Delhi to pressurize Junagadh into reversing their decision. This began by putting an embargo on the state by stopping the supplies of essential items like food and coal. Indian troops were deployed around the region as a show of strength. Bhutto kept on asking Pakistan for military and financial assistance, but the help never came. This was because of the fact that, before independence, Jinnah had not been properly briefed about the disarray Pakistani military was in after the partition by his British military chiefs. Violence started in the State and encouraged by the Kathiawad people's Front, a provisional government, the subjects of the State started a demonstration against the Nawab, who fled to Karachi with his family. On October 27th, Bhutto fled to Pakistan after requesting the Union Government to take over the

administration. A plebiscite was organized by the Government of India on February 29, 1949 where out of 2, 01,457 registered voters, 1,90,870 exercised their franchise, of which only 90 cast their votes in favour of Pakistan. According to Patel, the Government had tried its best through negotiations to come to a peaceful settlement in the interest of the country. Though the things were moving in the proper direction, the Government of India had to take drastic steps due to a sudden change in the Nawab's policy, to bring the state under its control. Patel said that "in such cases possession is nine-tenths of the law". Finally, Junagadh was merged in Kathiawad States, which became a part of the Gujarat state. The way Junagadh was made to accede to India was very clear from legal and democratic point of view. Junagadh's accession to Pakistan raised lot of public controversy but from the point of the guideline of the British Government's partition programme, Junagadh had to accede to India on geographical and economical grounds, though the state was ruled by a Muslim ruler. Taking the population into consideration the state having a majority of Hindus should be a part of India. On similar consideration, Bahawalpur, a state adjacent to India and Pakistan was allowed to accede to Pakistan. The Pakistan government still recognizes Nawab Mohmmad Jahngir Khanji, the grandson of the last Nawab Mohmmad Mahabat Khanji as the present Nawab of Junagarh and installed him with all pomp as the eleventh Nawab of a State in exile on October 9, 1991.

HYDERABAD- THE OPTIONS AVAILABLE

Most of the states acceded to India, Hyderabad, the largest of the native states with a Muslim ruler and 86% Hindu population created a threat to the solidarity of the country. It was located in the south-central region of the Indian subcontinent, and was ruled, from 1724 until 1948, by a hereditary Nizam. In 1947, under the rule of the then Nizam, Osman Ali Khan, it was the oldest existing Muslim Empire in India. Although landlocked, with an area of over 200,000 sq. km and a population of over 16 million, Hyderabad was self-sufficient in food, cotton and coal. The Nizam owned over 10% of the land of the state and most of the rest was owned by large landlords and very rich nobles. The bulk of the population, both Muslims and Hindus, worked as factory hands, artisans, labourers and peasants. The Nizam had ascended the throne as far back as in 1911. It did not have any access to the sea but the Nizam had high aspirations and wanted to proclaim sovereignty after the paramountcy was withdrawn. In order to negotiate with the Nizam, Lord Mountbatten was chosen and Sardar agreed to this. Sardar knew that, if the problem was handled by Mountbatten, it would be good for India since international and communal repercussions could be avoided. However, the decision on any point of controversy beyond the agreed formula was vested in the Congress High command only. The negotiations with the representatives of the Nizam started in July, 1947 but an accord could not be reached. Sardar clearly indicated that Nizam should accede to the Dominion of India in line with the instrument of Accession prepared for the other states. Sardar stated that the Nizam should follow the same path as the other states and in case he did not agree to the same, he should agree to allow the people of the state to decide the issue of accession. But, in spite of the best efforts of Mountbatten, the negotiations failed.

On 15th August, 1947, the same day India became independent, the Nizam declared the independence of Hyderabad. Ultimately with great reluctance an extension of two months was granted to Hyderabad to decide about the accession. After some more discussions with a number of delegates from Hyderabad, some concessions were granted by Sardar to the Nizam and the Standstill Agreement for one year and the collateral letters were signed on 29th November, 1947. The same day Sardar made a statement in the Constituent Assembly and explained that the period of one year granted to the Nizam would be helpful for final accession. Thus, he agreed with the settlement reached by the government on the ground that

accession of Hyderabad would be peaceful. Lord Mountbatten also crafted an alternative proposal called the Heads of Agreement, which called for the disbandment of the Razakars and restriction of the Hyderabad army, for the Nizam to hold a plebiscite and elections for a constituent assembly, and for eventual accession. While India would control Hyderabad's foreign affairs, the deal allowed Hyderabad to set up a parallel government and delay accession. The Nizam however dismissed the plan therefore hastening the ultimate showdown.

INTERNAL CHAOS

In spite of Standstill Agreement for one year, the Nizam did not give up his hope of attaining complete independence with the help of foreign powers. His doubtful actions, were reported to Sardar by K.M. Munshi, other trusted people and the reports of the news-papers regarding the reign of terror and the oppression of the Hindu Community. The Nizam was supported by Ittihad-ul-Muslimeen party which in 1946-47 was getting increasingly radicalized by its new leader, Kasim Razvi. Under him, the Ittihad had developed a militia called the 'Razakars' whose armed members demanded an independent Hyderabad. The Razakars started arson and looting in the neighbouring States. The Razakars saw the entire struggle in communal light while the Congress on the other hand saw it as a fight between democracy and autocracy. As months passed the tension grew as there were rumours of arms supply to Hyderabad from Pakistan and the flood of Hindu refugees kept flowing into adjoining Indian provinces. In Telangana, large groups of peasants, aided by the Communist Party of India and Andhra Mahasabha, revolted against local Hindu and Muslim landlords, and also came into direct confrontation with the Razakars, in what became known as the Telangana Rebellion. Meanwhile, parties like the Hyderabad State Congress were involved in nonviolent protests against the Nizam's rule. The Nizam wanted to represent his case to the Security Council to internationalize the issue. The Nizam's ambitions gained strength from the support of the Conservative Party of Britain. Even Winston Churchill stood in support of the Nizam and speaking in the House of Commons argued that Britain had a personal obligation not to allow one of its friendly states that had declared its sovereignty to be strangled, starved out or actually overborne by violence. The Nizam and specially the Razakars found further strength from the support shown by Pakistan. Jinnah had declared to Mountbatten that if Congress attempted to take over Hyderabad, every Muslim in the subcontinent would rise to defend it.

OPERATION POLO

When the situation was becoming alarming, Sardar intimated Nehru that the time came to tell Hyderabad that the Nizam should accede unconditionally. Sardar sought information from defense ministry and was informed that in case of any military action, it would not take more than three weeks to subdue the forces of Hyderabad. Though Nehru was hesitant due to the international reaction, Sardar was firm in his stand. It was decided that military would march into Hyderabad and C. Rajagopalachari, the then Governor-general called a meeting of the cabinet to regularize the action. On 13th September 1948 Indian troops invaded Hyderabad from all points of the compass in a campaign code named "Operation Polo" because at that time, Hyderabad state had some 17 polo grounds, the largest number in India. The fighting lasted four days and was mostly between the Indian army and the Razakars. Around 32 Indian soldiers were killed in the operation while the losses suffered by Hyderabad state forces and Irregular forces combined were 1,863 killed, 122 wounded, and 3,558 captured. Hyderabad was captured within a week's time. Though a lot of people were happy with the integration, there were some who were not. This led to many communal riots, according to very conservative estimates, around 27,000 to 40,000 died "during and after the police action".

Aftermath There were suggestions regarding the dividing Hyderabad into three linguistic parts but Sardar indicated that this would be done at an appropriate time, if necessary. With the merger of the State with India, the next step for financial and social integration started automatically. For his final accession to India, the Nizam was rewarded with the designation of Rajpramukh ie governor of the newly formed state of Hyderabad but resigned from this office when the states were re-organized in 1956 on linguistic basis and large parts of Hyderabad state went to Bombay State, Andhra Pradesh and Gujarat.

KASHMIR

The state was ruled by a Hindu ruler, whereas the majority population was Muslim. It occupied a very important strategic position. Maharaja Hari Singh, a Hindu, equally hesitant about acceding to either India, felt his mostly Muslim subjects would not like joining a Hindu majority nation or Pakistan, an eventuality which he would personally prefer to avoid. He personally believed that Kashmir could exercise its right to stay independent, a belief Sheikh Abdullah, the leader of Kashmir's largest political party, the National Conference backed. Pakistan coveted the Himalayan kingdom, while Indian leaders including Gandhi and Nehru, hoped that the kingdom would join India. Hari Singh signed a Standstill Agreement (preserving status quo) with Pakistan, but still withheld his decision by August 15.

TRIBAL ATTACK AND THE FIRST KASHMIR WAR

Till August 15th, 1947 Kashmir did not accede to India. Sardar knew the importance of Kashmir from its geographical position and wanted to tackle the problem himself as the Minister of the States, but Nehru was willing to deal with Kashmir, and Sardar did not object to it. Pakistan, concerned about the lack of movement on the front, attempted to force the issue by permitting the incursions of tribals from the North-West Frontier, followed by regular forces. On October 22, 1947, about 5,000 tribesmen led by Pakistani Army regulars attacked the region and quickly captured large parts of it. Instead of exploiting their initial success, however, the tribesmen stopped to loot and plunder, which gave a breathing space to the Raja of Kashmir. The question of sending the assistance of the Army of India to help the Maharaja rebuff an armed attack by the intruders was discussed at a meeting. Such assistance came on the condition of the Maharaja signing the Instrument of Accession, which he then did. In a panic, Maharaja Hari Singh signed the Instrument of Accession, becoming part of India, the same day. The raiders were just five kilometers from the capital, Srinagar. India decided to send an agent to Kashmir and Kunwar Sir Daleep Singh was posted as Agent in Jammu. India offered military assistance to the Kashmiri Government, which lacked an organized military. Indian troops secured Jammu, Srinagar and the valley itself during the First Kashmir War, but the intense fighting flagged with the onset of winter, which made much of the state impassable.

CEASEFIRE AND THE UN INVOLVEMENT

Prime Minister Nehru, recognizing the degree of international attention brought to bear on the dispute, declared a ceasefire and sought U.N. arbitration with the promise of a plebiscite. Patel had argued against both, describing Kashmir as a bilateral dispute and its accession as justified by international law. Patel had feared that the U.N.'s involvement would stall the process and allow Pakistan to reinforce its presence in Kashmir. Additionally, the outcome of a plebiscite remained highly uncertain. At the instance of Mountbatten, the Kashmir dispute was referred to the United Nations on 1st January, 1948 of which Patel was skeptical. There, India accused Pakistan of sending both regular troops and tribesmen into J&K. This led to the establishment of the U.N. Commission in India and Pakistan (UNCIP) by the Security

Council to assess the claims and counterclaims of the two countries. Although Pakistan initially denied any involvement, it later admitted that its army had been involved in the aggression. On August 13, 1948, the UNCIP passed a resolution asking Pakistan to withdraw its troops and tribesmen from J&K. "Once Pakistan withdraws them, the administration by the local authorities needs to be restored, India will reduce its troops to the barest minimum and then a plebiscite will be held to ascertain the wishes of the people of the state." The cease-fire went into effect on January 1, 1949, and the cease-fire line became the Line of Control (LOC), which later became de-facto border of India and Pakistan. By taking the matter to the U.N., India internationalized the issue and made Pakistan a party in the issue. By signing the Instrument of Accession, however, Maharaja Hari Singh had made J&K part of India. This was completely legal under the Indian Independence Act of 1947, signed by both India and Pakistan, which gave sovereignty of the state to Maharaja Hari Singh after the lapse of British Paramountcy. The Act contained no provision for ascertaining the wishes of the people of the princely states through plebiscite. It was thus completely wrong on the part of India to agree to a plebiscite in a territory that was a legal part of India. Nevertheless, the plebiscite was conditional upon Pakistan withdrawing its troops and tribesmen from the state and restoration of the administration to the local authorities. In last 50 years, Pakistan has not fulfilled the first two conditions.

With the accession of the State of Jammu and Kashmir to India, jurisdiction in matters of External Affairs, Defence and Communications was transferred to the Government of India and the Union Parliament was given power to make laws for the State for the purposes of those three matters only. In June 1949, the Yuvraj Karan Singh, on the advice of his Council of Ministers nominated four representatives to the Indian Constituent Assembly. Whereas all the other 564 Princely States decided to surrender all their residual autonomy to the Indian Union and accepted all the terms of the Indian Constitution in full, the State of Jammu and Kashmir decided to retain its autonomy. Moreover, under clause (7) of the Instrument of Accession, the State of Jammu and Kashmir did not commit itself to the acceptance of any future Constitution of India nor fetter its discretion to enter into agreements with the Government of India under any such future Constitution. So, the Government of Jammu and Kashmir did not accept the Constitution of India as a Constitution for the State. Even after accession to India Dominion, the State of Jammu and Kashmir continued to be governed by the Jammu and Kashmir Constitution Act, 1939. The Government of India could not force the State to accept the Constitution for that would violate the agreed terms of the association of Kashmir with India. The State had voluntarily surrendered three matters only and the Government of India could not enlarge the sphere of its jurisdiction at its own discretion. So, whereas the Constitution of India laid down Constitutional provisions, not only for the former Provinces of British India but also for the other Princely States as full-fledged Constituent units of the Union, in the case of Kashmir, it had to make special provisions to cover that particular case. In 1957, Kashmir officially integrated into the Union, but with special provisions made for it in the Constitution's Article 370. The north western portion remaining under control of the Pakistan army remains today as Pakistan-administered Kashmir.

CONCLUSION

The Indian Independence Act of 1947 gave princely states an option to accede to the newly born dominions India or Pakistan or continue as an independent sovereign state. At that time more than 500 princely states have covered 48 percent of the area of pre Independent India and constituted 28% of its population. These kingdoms were not legally part of British India, but in reality, they were completely subordinate to the British Crown. For the British these states were the necessary allies, to keep in check the rise of other colonial powers and

nationalist tendencies in India. Accordingly, the princes were given autonomy over their territories, but the British acquired for themselves the right to appoint ministers and get military support as and when required. Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel (India's first deputy prime minister and the home minister) with the assistance of V.P. Menon (the secretary of the Ministry of the States) was given the formidable task of integrating the princely states. From invoking the patriotism of the princes to remind them of the possibility of anarchy on event of their refusal to join, Patel kept trying to convince them to join India. He also introduced the concept of "privy purses"— a payment to be made to royal families for their agreement to merge with India. Bikaner, Baroda and few other states from Rajasthan were the first ones to join the union. There were several other states that were adamant to not join India. Some of them thought this to be the best moment to acquire independent statehood, while there were others who wanted to become a part of Pakistan.

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